

A STUDY ON FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to examine the roles of customer’s attitude, health consciousness, safety concern and moral on the subject of organic foods. An abstract model is tested via structural and non-probability sampling modelling. There were six critical parameters were found to impact the consumer attitude and consciousness towards organic foods. For this purpose a sample of 110 was collected from the respondents were percentage analysis was used as a tool to analyse the data. The conclusion is that more training programs can be given to the customers so that awareness about the organic foods can be increased which leads to increase in volume for the companies selling organic foods.

Key Words: Organic Foods, Consumer Attitude & Training Programs

Introduction:

Organic foods are foods produced by methods that comply with the standards of organic farming. Standards vary worldwide; however, organic farming in general, features practices that strive to foster cycling of resources, promote ecological balance, and conserve biodiversity. Organizations regulating organic products may choose to restrict the use of certain pesticides and fertilizers in farming. In general, organic foods are also usually not processed using irradiation, industrial solvents or synthetic food additives.

Legal Definition:

Organic food production is a self-regulated industry with government oversight in some countries, distinct from private gardening. Currently, the European Union, the United States, Canada, Japan, and many other countries require producers to obtain special certification based on government-defined standards in order to market food as organic within their borders. In the context of these regulations, foods marketed as organic are produced in a way that complies with organic standards set by national governments and international organic industry trade organizations.

Introduction to Customer Attitude:

Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer’s (1) beliefs about, (2) feelings about, (3) and behavioral intentions toward some object--within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object.

Need of the Study:

The need of the study is that demand is growing as incidences of food adulteration are repeatedly reported on in global media and consumer consciousness of natural, healthy and safe foods rises. New food safety legislation is also working towards improving the safety standards of food and, at the same time, consumers are increasingly willing to pay for organic foods as their disposable incomes rise.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objective: To study the level of acceptance of various factors related to organic food.

Secondary Objectives:

- ✓ To know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food.
- ✓ To know the problems and issues faced by organic food.
- ✓ To know the demographic profile of the respondents.

Scope of the Study: The study is about analyzing the perception and attitude of customers towards organic food usage on Coimbatore. This may help the manufacturers related to organic food to develop themselves related to production and marketing strategy which will lead to increase in profit of their firm.

Research Methodology: Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem by appealing the various research techniques along with the logic behind the problem. Thus research methodology is a scientific way of solving the research problem.

Area of the Study: The area of the study is Coimbatore city only.

Population of the Study: The population of the study is indefinite.

Sampling Design: For the purpose of this study the data were collected from 110 respondents using random sampling technique.

Sampling Size: The sample size of the research is 110 respondents.

Method of Data Collection:

- ✓ Primary Data: Questionnaire
- ✓ Secondary Data: Books, journals and magazines.

Tools Used for Study: Percentage Analysis

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Due to time constraint, the sample size is limited to 110 & the study area is restricted to Coimbatore.
- ✓ Respondent may fail to express their opinions and beliefs.
- ✓ There may be a bias in collecting the data.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variable	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	Below 20 years	77	70
	21-30 years	33	30
	Total	110	100
Gender	Male	68	61.8
	Female	42	38.2
	Total	110	100
Marital Status	Married	3	2.7
	Unmarried	107	97.3
	Total	110	100
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	7	6.4
	Up to school	35	31.8
	Graduate	58	52.7
	Others	10	9.1
	Total	110	100
Occupation	Employee	7	6.4
	Business	59	53.6
	Profession	31	28.2
	Others	13	11.8
	Total	110	100
Monthly Income	Less than 10000	15	13.6
	10001-20000	25	22.7
	20001-30000	55	50
	More than 30001	15	13.6
	Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about the age of the respondents were out of 110 respondents 70% are from the age group of below 20 years and 30% are from the age group of 21 to 30 years. 61.8% are male and 38.2% are female. 2.7% are married and 97.3% are unmarried. 6.4% are illiterates, 31.8% have completed their schoolings, 52.7% are graduates and 9.1% are from other courses. 6.4% are employees, 53.6% are business people, 28.2% are professionals and 11.8% are doing other jobs. 13.6% are earning less than 10000, 22.7% are earning from 10001-20000, 50% are earning from 20001-30000, 13.6% are earning more than 30001. 58.2% are from joint family and 41.8% are from nuclear family.

Level of Acceptance towards Reliability of Organic Products:

	Frequency	Percent
Agree	48	43.6
Neutral	27	24.5
Disagree	19	17.3
Strongly Disagree	16	14.5
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about level of acceptance towards reliability of organic products were out of 110 respondents 43.6% agree, 24.5% are neutral, 17.3% disagree and 14.5% strongly disagree. It shows that most 43.6% of the respondents agree for reliability of organic products.

Level of Acceptance towards Tastier:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	12	10.9
Agree	28	25.5
Neutral	34	30.9
Disagree	18	16.4
Strongly Disagree	18	16.4
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about level of acceptance towards taste of organic products were out of 110 respondents 10.9% strongly agree, 25.5% agree, 30.9% are neutral, 16.4% disagree and 16.4% strongly disagree. It shows that most 30.9% of the respondents are neutral towards taste of organic products.

Level of Acceptance towards Very Expensive:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	16	14.5
Agree	27	24.5
Neutral	44	40
Disagree	20	18.2
Strongly Disagree	3	2.7
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about level of acceptance towards very expensive of organic products were out of 110 respondents 14.5% strongly agree, 24.5% agree, 40% are neutral, 18.2% disagree and 2.7% strongly disagree. It shows that most 40% of the respondents are neutral about very expensive of organic products.

Satisfaction towards Organic Foods:

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	97	88.2
No	13	11.8
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about satisfaction towards organic foods were out of 110 respondents 88.2% are satisfied and 11.8% are not satisfied. It shows that most 88.2% of the respondents are satisfied towards organic foods.

Level of Acceptance towards Organic Foods Caring About Environment:

	Frequency	Percent
Agree	19	17.3
Neutral	31	28.2
Disagree	36	32.7
Strongly Disagree	24	21.8
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about level of acceptance towards organic foods caring about environment were out of 110 respondents 17.3% agree, 28.2% are neutral, 32.7% disagree and 21.8% strongly disagree. It shows that most 32.7% of the respondents disagree for organic foods caring about environment.

Level of Acceptance towards Lower Price for Organic Food:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	5	4.5
Agree	40	36.4

Neutral	49	44.5
Disagree	11	10
Strongly Disagree	5	4.5
Total	110	100

Interpretation:

The above shows about level of acceptance towards lower price for organic food were out of 110 respondents 4.5% strongly agree, 36.4% agree, 44.5% are neutral, 10% disagree and 4.5% strongly disagree. It shows that most 44.5% of the respondents are neutral for acceptance towards lower price for organic food.

Findings:

- ✓ Most 70% of the respondents are from the age group of below 20 years.
- ✓ Most 70% of the respondents are male in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum 52.7% of the respondents are graduates in our survey.
- ✓ Most 53.6% of the respondents are doing business.
- ✓ Maximum 50% of the respondents are earning from 20001-30000 as their monthly income.
- ✓ Most 58.2% of the respondents are from joint family.
- ✓ Maximum 42.7% of the respondents are having 3-4 members in their family.
- ✓ Most 42.7% of the respondents are from semi urban area.
- ✓ Maximum 43.6% of the respondents agree for reliability of organic products.
- ✓ Most 30.9% of the respondents are neutral towards taste of organic products.
- ✓ Maximum 41.8% of the respondents agree for nutrition value.
- ✓ Most 44.5% of the respondents purchase once in a week.
- ✓ Maximum 34.5% of the respondents purchase organic products through online.
- ✓ Most 50% of the respondents purchase fruits.
- ✓ Maximum 36.4% of the respondents said as television for person influencing to buy organic products.
- ✓ Most 49.1% of the respondents said as two years for interest towards organic foods.
- ✓ Maximum 77.3% of the respondents said that they are not purchasing the product even though they are less expensive.
- ✓ Most 36.4% of the respondents agree towards providing healthier food for them and their family by purchasing organic products
- ✓ Maximum 41.8% of the respondents agree for level of acceptance towards organic food taste better than non organic food.
- ✓ Most 37.3% of the respondents are neutral for purchasing organic products means they support local farmers and agriculture.
- ✓ Maximum 32.7% of the respondents disagree for organic foods carrying about environment.
- ✓ Most 35.5% of the respondents agree for fertilize free of organic means
- ✓ Maximum 44.5% of the respondents are neutral for acceptance towards lower price for organic food.
- ✓ Most 38.2% of the respondents agree for wider product selection for organic food.
- ✓ Maximum 30.9% of the respondents strongly agree towards strong influence from friends.
- ✓ Most 38.2% of the respondents are neutral for healthiness of organic foods based on scientific evidence.
- ✓ Maximum 66.36% of the respondents said that they are not facing any problem while using organic food product.
- ✓ Most 43.2% of the respondents said that they are facing allergy problems.
- ✓ Maximum 88.2% of the respondents are satisfied towards organic foods.

Suggestions:

More training programs can be given to the customers so that awareness about the organic foods can be increased which leads to increase in volume for the companies selling organic foods. Package of product: Provide a good packing facilities to specific product can be made by the companies. There is all very important is to develop more marketing area as there is no regulated market facility in organic product.

Conclusion:

Organic food production is a self-regulated industry with government oversight in some countries, distinct from private gardening. The main objective of the study is to know the consumer awareness level of attitude towards organic food. For this purpose a sample of 110 was collected from the respondents were percentage analysis was used as a tool to analyse the data. The conclusion is that more training programs can be given to the customers so that awareness about the organic foods can be increased which leads to increase in volume for the companies selling organic foods.

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